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A new open access strategy for the Netherlands

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Preface

Academia is in a global transition to a more open and inclusive way of conducting, publishing, and evaluating scientific research and education¹. In 2022, the Dutch higher educational organisations, funders, and service providers, created a shared Ambition Document for advancing Open Science in the Netherlands. One of the four strategic goals in this ambition document is *'the removal of barriers to creating, reading, reusing and evaluating all Dutch scholarly output, so everyone can access scientific knowledge in a sustainable way and benefit from it'*².

In moving towards this goal, the Universities of the Netherlands (UNL) have been successful in increasing the open access to peer-reviewed articles to 95% in 2024³, relying heavily on read-and-publish deals with primarily revenue-driven publishers.

However, changing prioritisation of strategic considerations (see Annex 1), developments in the scholarly publishing landscape, a change in the system of recognition and rewards, the rise of the use of AI in publishing, and geopolitical developments (including considerable budget cuts within academia), call for a critical revision of the current open access strategy, covering a diversity of routes and types of scholarly output⁴.

This document is the result of a thorough process involving many national stakeholders. In late 2023 an internal white paper⁵ on issues with the current situation of open access in the Netherlands was discussed by the association of Dutch university libraries (UKB), sparking a discussion on a new vision and strategy for open access. In April 2024 the national event "What do we want (or not want) from publishers?"⁶ was organised; in June 2024 several scenarios were discussed during in the Bestuurlijk Overleg Open Science, among the key Open Science stakeholders in the Netherlands (e.g., Dutch higher educational organisations, funders, service providers, and the government⁷). An UNL/UKB working group was tasked with developing action lines for a strategy. In May 2025 the dilemmas for different actions were discussed during a national event "Shaping a new Open Access Strategy". In November 2025 this document was discussed by UKB; and in December 2025, the presidents of the Dutch Universities (UNL-SSPG) adopted this strategy for the universities.

This strategy was written by a working group of university experts, in consultation with members of the broader Dutch Open Access community and researchers. These and other Dutch stakeholders are invited to build upon this strategy by adding different perspectives and action lines (e.g. with a focus on other publication types).

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1. UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021): <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>
2. NPOS Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda (2022): <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/binaries/rijksoverheid/documenten/rapporten/2022/12/07/bijlage-npos-2030-ambitiedocument-en-rolling-agenda/bijlage-npos-2030-ambitiedocument-en-rolling-agenda.pdf>
3. UNL - Nederland koploper met 95 procent Open Access, maar vernieuwing strategie is nodig (2025): <https://www.universiteitenvan nederland.nl/actueel/nieuws/nederland-koploper-met-95-procent-open-access-maar-vernieuwing-strategie-is-nodig>
4. We define scholarly output as any element of research that can be represented as a digital object and can be made FAIR and freely accessible via an Open Access licence. In addition to peer-reviewed articles, this includes outputs such as professional publications, conference proceedings, monographs, reports, protocols, and presentations.
5. White paper open access, versie 2.0. (2023). UKB Werkgroep Licenties: Matthijs van Otegem en Kurt De Belder
6. The report of the event "What do we want (or not want) from publishers?": <https://zenodo.org/records/11384105>
7. I.e. the organisations that signed the covenant on OSNL: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/convenanten/2023/03/15/bijlage-convenant-regieorgaan-open-science>

Problems with the current situation

The current strategy for open scholarly communication has the following issues (for a more extensive description of the current strategy and its issues, see [Annex 2](#)):

Lack of control over copyright and metadata

- Lack of academic and digital sovereignty
- No copyright retention or open licensing

Dependency on big revenue-driven publishers

- Decreased knowledge diversity (e.g. in publication types and inclusion of other knowledge systems)
- Conflicts of interest between innovation and profits
- Limited flexibility in current consortium agreements (only 'bulk sales' possible in big deals)
- Built-in incentives to publish more

Open Access Strategy 2025 - 2035 / Why

Unsustainable financial model

- The shift of costs from reading to publishing with an author-pay-model was long thought to be possible in a cost-neutral way, but has proven not to be (due to power of big market-players)
- Current cost allocation model is under pressure
- No transparency in cost structures

Quality under pressure

- Decreased trustworthiness of information due to low-quality content and peer review (e.g. paper mills⁸, or AI-generated⁹)
- Lack of transparency and accountability in quality control

Clash between recognition & rewards and ranking metrics

- Perverse incentives for quantity of publications over their quality
- Reliance on flawed metrics for promotions (H-index, journal impact factor¹⁰)

Lack of equity and openness

- Inequitable access to publishing for less-affluent researchers and institutions

Our current strategy from 2013, with its dependency on the author-pay model and reliance on big, revenue-driven publishers, has reached its limits.

Internationally, the Netherlands is part of a large, growing group of countries and (global) organisations that share a concern about the current status quo of scholarly communication, including the European Union¹¹; the global International Science Council (ISC)¹²; several European countries (e.g. Norway¹³, Sweden¹⁴ and Switzerland¹⁵), funders^{16,17,18}; and groups of institutions (e.g. through the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information¹⁹).

8. Sanderson, K. (2024) Science's fake-paper problem: high-profile effort will tackle paper mills. Nature 626, 17-18, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00159-9>

9. Naddaf, M. (2025) AI is transforming peer review — and many scientists are worried. Nature 639, 852-854, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-00894-7>

10. Seglen, P.O. (1997) Why the impact factor of journals should not be used for evaluating research. BMJ 314, 498-502:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2126010/pdf/9056804.pdf>

11. Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing (2023):

<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8827-2023-INIT/en/pdf>

12. <https://council.science/actionplan/why-scientific-publishing-matters/publishingprinciples/>

13. Strategi for vitenskapelig publisering etter (2024): <https://www.openscience.no/en/media/3775/download?inline?inline>

14. Charting Sweden's path beyond transformative agreements (2023): <https://suhf.se/app/uploads/2023/10/Charting-Swedens-path-beyond-transformative-agreements-%E2%80%93-analysis-and-proposals-for-strategic-direction-October-2023.pdf>

15. Swiss National Open Access Strategy I (2024): https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Access/Swiss-National-Open-Access-Strategy-2024-en.pdf

16. <https://www.gatesfoundation.org/about/policies-and-resources/open-access-policy>

17. <https://wellcome.org/grant-funding/guidance/open-access-guidance/open-access-policy>

18. cOAlition S Strategy 2026-2030: <https://www.coalition-s.org/coalitions-strategy-2026-2030/>

19. Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10958522>

A vision for the future of open access

If the Dutch universities and other stakeholders continue on the current course, this will lead to an even more uniform publishing landscape with little knowledge diversity, dominated by a few large revenue-driven entities with prohibitively high profits, at the expense of autonomy, room for innovation, equity, and sometimes quality control. Therefore, we should now aim for a flexible, inclusive, and sustainable open access ecosystem that fosters:

- Control over copyright and metadata
- More diversity in the scholarly communication landscape
- Sustainable innovation in publishing infrastructure
- Transparency and accountability for quality and integrity
- Empowerment of academic communities to create publication strategies
- Equity and openness

The most common routes to open access in the Netherlands are:

Community-driven open access

Many full open access journals and platforms do not charge APCs to authors. Costs for these journals and platforms are usually borne by the academic community, such as societies, universities, libraries, funders or other stakeholders. There are many such journals that serve a rich diversity of academic communities, languages, and publication types.

Revenue-driven open access

Other publishers charge an article processing charge (APC) to the author for making their article openly accessible, or, as part of the Read & Publish agreements with large publishers, institutions pay publishers to enable their researchers to publish open access in their collection of journals.

Institutional repository-based open access

Researchers can deposit digital copies of their articles into their organisation's open-access repository, often after an embargo period. This self-archiving in institutional repositories is often a fallback option for articles that are originally not published open access. University libraries jointly developed the project "You share, we take care" to help researchers depositing their works after an embargo period of 6 months. More and more funders have grant conditions that predate possible later conditions set by the publisher, allowing researchers to share their work through repositories directly without restrictions.

Towards the future

To realise this vision, this proposed open access strategy highlights the need to diversify our spending into several routes to open access, and to reclaim our autonomy over scholarly communication. Universities need to organise and support academic publishing, as well as influence authors' publishing behaviour. This may necessitate extra investments, but the focus of this strategy lies on reallocating budget while maintaining cost-neutrality. Some of the action lines mentioned below have received funding for the next few years (*see related current initiatives*); all investments will be subject to a diligent decision-making process.

Together, these actions should lead to a more harmonised, flexible, multi-route approach which emphasises sustainability and academic values, and provide sufficient room for various disciplines and communities to walk their own path, while at the same time adhering to the same national open access strategy.

Open Access Strategy 2025 - 2035 / Actions

To avoid an even more uniform publishing landscape, dominated by a few large revenue-driven entities with prohibitively high profits, and to reclaim the autonomy of the academic community, the following actions are needed:

Develop institutional publication policies

- Engage in dialogues with faculties/ research departments on publishing strategies
- Revise institutional Open Access policies
- Develop new practices for recognising research and researchers

Invest in community-driven publishing

- Create a framework for evaluating and supporting community-driven initiatives
- Reallocate a part of the deal budget for investment in alternative publication options
- Incentivise preprint publications and the publish-review-curate model
- Foster a diversity of publication platforms

Reconsider deals with publishers

- Create a roadmap for incremental adjustments to the negotiations
- Foster international collaboration in negotiations with publishers
- Adapt cost allocation models to facilitate community-driven publication strategies
- Create an efficient and transparent workflow for publication finances

Strengthen the role of institutional repositories

- Improve Taverne uptake and institutionalise retention of copyright
- Establish a harmonised copyright policy
- Lobby at the European Commission for a stronger legal mandate for repository-based open access
- Cooperate with funders to align funder mandates

1. Develop institutional publication policies

Publication policies of Dutch Universities and other knowledge institutions need to empower research communities to make publishing decisions. These policies should align with revised recognition and rewards and Open Science mandates (e.g. increasing value of equitable and responsible publishing venues, rewarding efforts for scholar-led/community-driven publishing, more focus on quality and impact instead of quantity, etc).

University registration policies, infrastructure and workflows need to be reassessed so that they allow for the sharing and promotion of preprints, author-accepted manuscripts, and connecting different manuscript versions (and/or output types like data and software).

Actions:

- **Engage in dialogues with faculties/ research departments on publishing strategies**, intended to develop faculty/ institutional publication strategies.
Goals: raise awareness about publication culture in which quality, fitness-for-purpose, integrity, openness, as well as academic and societal relevance will outweigh quantity and external markers of prestige. Support faculties and institutes in making policy choices regarding scholarly publishing that promotes the progress of science and advances knowledge for the benefit of society.
- **Revise institutional open access policies**
Goal: to extend existing open access policies to reflect the diversity of publication strategies of research units and the diversity of publication options now available (e.g. preprinting, other publication types). These policies should take into account the responsible use of AI in scholarly communication.
- **Develop new practices for recognising research and researchers** through the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA ²⁰), the national and local Recognition & Rewards programmes, and Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP ²¹), supporting the principles of The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA ²²) in close collaboration with the research community. This includes rewarding researchers for posting preprints, (open) peer review reports, and open data by explicitly including those practices in their assessment; and instructing assessors that journal names, impact factors, and number of journal articles will play no role in researcher assessment. ²³

20. Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment: <https://coara.eu/>

21. Strategy Evaluation Protocol:

<https://www.universiteitenvanonderland.nl/onderwerpen/onderzoek/evaluatie-protocol-onderzoek-sep> Strategy Evaluation Protocol 2021–2027 | KNAW

22. San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (2013): <https://sfidora.org/>

23. Towards Responsible Publishing (2023): <https://zenodo.org/records/8398480>

Goal: improving the reward system by acknowledging a wider selection of outputs and versions, and decreasing the importance of bibliometrics, will make it easier for researchers to pursue one of the various open access routes.

Related initiatives:

- Open Science Monitoring Framework (OSNL tender, granted to CWTS/Dialogic).
- Recognition & Rewards for Open Science projects at Dutch higher education organisations (OSNL grants)
- The UNL Vision on Publication Culture offers a guideline for future policy developments involving publishing (approved by UNL SOO on 5 December 2025)

2. Invest in community-driven publishing

As described above, our dependency on big, revenue-driven publishers is problematic. In 2023, the Council of the European Union similarly concluded that it is important to move towards a more open, equitable and sustainable scholarly publishing system²⁴. There is a large diversity in well-respected and community-driven publication outlets (e.g. diamond, publish-review-curate publishing platforms, etc), which need structural investment in order to become a sustainable alternative to the revenue-driven route to open access.

This necessitates investments in alternative, community-driven, publication options, which can be achieved by redirecting (a portion of) the current budget for revenue-driven open access towards this goal²⁵.

Actions:

- **Create a framework for evaluating and supporting community-driven initiatives** to systematically invest in community-driven infrastructures/ publishers/ platforms/ journals, including university-led (diamond) open access publishers and the Netherlands University Presses (NUP's).

Goal: create a model for investment (informed by the publication strategies by research communities).

24. Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing (2023):

<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8827-2023-INIT/en/pdf>

25. Open Science Communities NL. (2025). Call to Commitment: A future-proof approach to Open Access Publishing in the Netherlands. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17697462>

- **Reallocate a part of the deal budget for investment in alternative publication options, informed by the institutional publication strategies**

Goal: this will increase sustainability and viability of these alternatives, and allows for a staggered and improved approach to upholding academic values.

- **Incentivise preprint publications²⁶ and the publish-review-curate model.**

Create a national framework which assigns intrinsic value to different versions of output (e.g. preprints²⁷).

Goal: Wide adoption of preprints increases the speed of dissemination, and paves the way for decoupling of three core functions of scholarly communication – publication, peer review, and curation – to ensure full and immediate sharing of scholarly outputs and retaining copyright.

- **Foster a diversity of publication platforms** to maximise societal impact and facilitate transparent dissemination of knowledge. For example, making use of existing collective open access research publishing services (e.g., Open Research Europe²⁸, Publinova²⁹), or supporting other subject-specific and national not-for-profit open access platforms that provide high-quality scholarly publishing services.

Goal: provide qualitative/reputable publication options besides revenue-driven venues.

Related initiatives:

- UNL/UKB-programme Diamond Open Access (2024-2026), with action lines:
 - Expertise Centre Diamond Open Access (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)
 - Capacity building for diamond open access platforms, with OpenJournals/ New University Presses (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)
 - Monitoring of diamond open access
- PRC-project (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)
- UKB Publishing Browser (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)
- Strengthening collective digital autonomy of the universities (UNL strategy under development)
- Netherlands University Presses (NUPs; started 2022)

26. National Programme Open Science Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda (2022): <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/binaries/rijksoverheid/documenten/rapporten/2022/12/07/bijlage-npos-2030-ambitiedocument-en-rolling-agenda/bijlage-npos-2030-ambitiedocument-en-rolling-agenda.pdf>

27. Waltman L., Rzayeva N., Pinfield S. (2025) The state of preprinting in Europe and the Netherlands. Leiden Madrics, doi: <https://doi.org/10.59350/h5cx3-7yn67>

28. <https://www.nwo.nl/nieuws/nwo-onderschrijft-aansluiting-bij-open-access-platform-open-research-europe-ore>

29. <https://publinova.nl/>

3. Reconsider deals with publishers

Currently, a limited number of scholarly communication organisations wield enormous market power. It is important to challenge their oligopoly, although it will not be easy to do this. Academic values (e.g. sovereignty, quality assurance, integrity, transparency, equity, etc.) and flexibility need to become more important - if not key - criteria within negotiations with publishers.

Actions:

- **Create a roadmap for incremental adjustments to the negotiations framework**, with academic values, autonomy and flexibility as key criteria³⁰, informed by the publication strategies by research communities. The criteria for negotiations should include a clear mandate for the negotiating consortium (e.g. is there collective university-wide support for walking away from a deal if our demands are not met?).

Demands include:

- *Retention of copyright and open licences.* Publishers may not require authors to relinquish their copyright and will publish the work under an open licence (e.g., CC-BY).
- *Open meta-information.* In April 2024, over 40 organisations, including Dutch universities, universities of applied sciences, and funders, signed the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, committing to make openness the default for the research information they use and produce³¹. The list of signatories, also from the Netherlands, is still growing. In line with this declaration, publishers should openly provide all metadata of published works for the purpose of open data analysis.
- *Permitting text and data mining of content and use for AI.* Publishers will provide automated access (e.g., through APIs) to subscribed content as a standard part of all contracts, without restrictions on non-consumptive, computational analysis of the corpus of subscribed content.
- *The publication process conforms to quality standards of the academic communities.*
- *Immediate deposition in repositories.* Publishers will immediately deposit scientific articles in institutional repositories upon publication, or will provide tools to facilitate immediate deposition.
- *Jurisdiction.* Contract terms under EU law (now, these are often under US law)

Goal: encourage publishers to increase adherence to public/academic values, without additional costs.

30. MIT Principles (2020): <https://libraries.mit.edu/scholarly/publishing/framework/>

31. Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10958522>

- **Foster international collaboration in negotiations with publishers**

Goal: expanding the consortium can improve our position within negotiations.

- **Adapt cost allocation models to facilitate community-driven publication strategies**

Goal: create room in our national cost allocation models (e.g., higher educational institutions and funders) for less dependency on revenue-driven open access publishers.

- **Create an efficient and transparent workflow for publication finances**, and implement this at every university/UMC. Establish an exchange workflow with funders for the sharing of funder details. The experiences of the current pilot-deal with PLoS can be used as an example.

Goal: full insight into publishing expenses allows the consortium, higher education institutions, faculties, and departments to more effectively manage publication expenditure and make policy decisions.

Related initiatives:

- Pilot deal with full open access publisher PLoS (2025)
- BROCCOLI (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)
- Barcelona Declaration & OA2020 Joint Task Force on Negotiating Openness of Publication Metadata ³²

4. Strengthen the role of institutional repositories

Work to expand the use of strategies to retain researchers' rights by adopting institutional strategies and exploring whether such strategies can be implemented at the national, European, and global levels.

This provides a safety net for scientific work and strengthens the position of UNL in negotiations with revenue-driven publishers.

32. Joint Task Force on Negotiating Openness of Publication Metadata (2025): https://barcelona-declaration.org/news/20251002_bd_oa2020_joint_taskforce/

Actions:

- **Improve Taverne uptake** (e.g., via author uploads) and institutionalise retention of copyright (e.g., via an institutional rights retention strategy, or RRS).
Goal: turns free repository-based routes into more valid open access options for researchers and university strategies.
- **Establish a harmonised copyright policy**³³, that settles who owns copyright for different academic outputs. Leiden University was the first of the Dutch universities to adopt copyright regulations³⁴.
Goal: offer universities legal tools for structural use of green options like Taverne and RRS.
- **Lobby at the European Commission for a stronger legal mandate for repository-driven open access**
Goal: connect a network of strong repositories and link these with service providers like OpenAIRE and OpenAlex.
- **Cooperate/lobby with funders to align funder mandates** with a wider variety of repository-based options, e.g. preprints and/or embargoed open access.
Goal: make repository-based open access more compliant and attractive to researchers.

Related initiatives:

- A sub-group of UKB-WGOA is investigating the feasibility of an institutional RRS
- Advice on Harmonizing Employer Copyright (November 2023), new working group since 2025
- DURF: strengthening the Netherlands research portal and institutional repositories (granted OSNL infrastructure proposal)

33. Advies Harmoniseren Auteursrecht (2023):

https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/files/publications/UNL_19723-12-Advies%20Harmoniseren%20Werkgeversauteursrecht-online.pdf

34. Leiden University copyright regulations (2025):

https://www.organisatiegids.universiteitleiden.nl/binaries/content/assets/algemeen/reglementen/leiden-university-employer-copyright-regulations_4.2.2025.pdf

Annex 1

Values and considerations

The ecosystem of scholarly publishing is multifaceted and complex. Several considerations should be taken into account when discussing scenarios for a new open access strategy:

- **Digital autonomy.** To guarantee scientific knowledge as a public good for collective benefit, it is important to consider the sustainability, governance, and financial models of scholarly infrastructure, (retention of) copyright and open licensing of scientific work. The risks of becoming more and more dependent on commercial/ revenue-driven or foreign providers and their terms of use in all stages of the research life cycle call for open (not-for-profit) alternatives for digital services and regulation. On top of that, the geopolitical reality is changing rapidly. When states exert direct or indirect influence on technology companies, it is naïve to think that universities can remain outside that sphere of power. Digital autonomy is a prerequisite for strong universities, strong science and a strong society. Academic freedom, research integrity, open science: all these principles are increasingly under pressure from closed ecosystems, shifting terms and conditions, and data flows that we can no longer see or control.

Concerted actions are needed to maintain (or retrieve) digital autonomy.

Achieving this requires action on multiple fronts ³⁵:

- We must look at adjustments to legislation and regulation.
- At sharper procurement conditions and increasing our collective purchasing power.
- At developing real alternatives, and at expanding our own capacity and expertise.
- And above all: at much stronger cooperation, nationally and with our European partners, with universities, governments and other public institutions.

Strengthening the collective digital autonomy of our universities is a high priority. And that means ensuring that the digital infrastructure we rely on supports our academic core values, rather than eroding them.

35. Based on the Terms of Reference for enhancing collective digital autonomy (SOO.50.05) - approved by SOO 5 December 2025

- **Quality and integrity.** An important aspect of a publication venue is the quality of the work published there. In the current situation, publishing, review and curation are often entwined into one process. This means that the quality of the published work in a journal/ publisher/ platform is linked to the quality assurances implemented in the publication process (e.g., peer review, editorial checks, etc.). There are issues with some journals and publishers in this regard.

For journals and platforms in which publication has been disentangled from review and curation, the situation is different.

- **Equity, diversity and inclusion.** Open Science embraces the diversity of topics, disciplines, practices, languages, outputs, and processes of different (scientific and societal) communities. The scientific community itself needs to be representative of the society it aims to serve. In the context of scholarly publication this means that access and opportunities to engage with scientific work should be open to everyone interested, regardless of their location, connections, and affluence.
- **Sustainability.** To make sure that scholarly knowledge is durably accessible for everyone, the sustainability of different routes to open access must be critically considered. This entails financial sustainability for keeping scholarly work openly accessible in the foreseeable future, but also sustainability of relevance for, and commitment from, a scholarly community.
- **Knowledge diversity.** In the past decades, academic publishing has become more privatised and commercialised, and publication cultures – and publications themselves – have become more homogenised. Scalability has advantages for efficiency and cost reduction through modularity and standardisation³⁶, but may also lead to a loss of bibliodiversity³⁷. A relevant alternative concept is ‘scaling small’, or “the move towards creating (loose) alliances, collectives, and cooperatives between scholar-led and not-for-profit publishing entities”³⁸, which may provide a similarly resilient structure as ‘upscaling’. Most discussions and strategies about open access pertain to peer-reviewed scholarly articles. This scope excludes other types of scholarly research publications (e.g. monographs, book chapters, edited volumes, conference proceedings, case notes), but also professional and popular publications. In this document, the scope is the full range of scholarly research publications.

Some of the current routes and actions are not suitable for all types of publications. As publication cultures differ significantly between scientific disciplines³⁹, the suitability of options may also differ between academic fields.

36. King, D. W. (2007). The cost of journal publishing: A literature review and commentary. *Learned Publishing*, 20(2), 20. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.1087/174148507X183551>

37. Ma, L., Buggle, J. and O'Neill, M. (2023) 'Open access at a crossroads: library publishing and bibliodiversity', *Insights: the UKSG journal*, 36(1), p. 10: <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.613>

38. Adema, J & Moore, S. (2021) 'Scaling Small; Or How to Envision New Relationalities for Knowledge Production', *Westminster Papers in Communication and Culture*. 16(1) :27-45. <https://doi.org/10.16997/wpcc.918>

39. Bosman, J., Kramer, B. (2019). Publication cultures and Dutch research output: a quantitative assessment. <https://zenodo.org/records/2643360>

- **Affordability.** With a growing number of publications by authors affiliated with Dutch universities, it is critical to consider the structural affordability of open scholarly publishing in the Netherlands, for the reader (should be free), for the author (preferably free, but at least affordable), and for institutions/consortia/governments (affordable, and in line with values and principles).

Here, it is important to distinguish between expenditures (e.g. payments to revenue-driven publishers necessary to maintain short-term operations) and investments (the creation of assets through funding publicly/community owned or governed infrastructures and other alternatives that generate value over time), and emphasize the strategic importance of diversifying spending: it is never wise to put all our eggs in one basket, especially not for a core process.

Annex 2

Status quo of open access to publications in the Netherlands

In 2013, the Dutch government explicitly expressed its support for open access: a letter to parliament set a goal to have at least 60% of article publications openly accessible by 2018, increasing to 100% by 2024 ⁴⁰.

Since then, the Dutch consortium has successfully increased the percentage of open access publications in the Netherlands: over 2024, 95% of peer-reviewed articles from Dutch universities is openly accessible. With this result, the Netherlands is, alongside the Scandinavian countries and the UK, ahead of the curve. UKB has developed a professional knowledge base (through the project UKBsis) that enables the consortium to closely monitor the performance of open access in the Netherlands with current and accurate data on types of open access, journals, licences, costs, etc, leading to information that guides new negotiations and decision-making.

The current level of open access was achieved via several routes, which are discussed below.

Revenue-driven open access

Big deals

Since 2015, the UNL/NFU consortium has entered into a portfolio of transformative Read & Publish agreements (R&P, or big deals) with major publishers. With these R&P agreements, institutions gained reading access, and allowed them to publish open access in a collection of journals at limited cost. Although these agreements have not made the foreseen transition from subscription models cost-neutral, the Dutch agreements are relatively cost-effective compared to some other countries' agreements ⁴¹. These deals pertain to peer-reviewed scholarly articles only.

In 2022, 39% of the openly accessible articles were published in hybrid journals that still have a subscription model (mostly through the above-mentioned agreements), or in journals not included in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) ⁴².

40. Brief van de Staatssecretaris van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap aan de Voorzitter van de Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal (2013): <https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/kst-31288-354.html>

41. Van der Graaf, M., Johnson, R. (2021). Deelrapport 1 van de Haalbaarheidsstudie 100% Open Access voor Nederlandse Onderzoekpublicaties (2021). <https://www.universiteitenvan nederland.nl/files/publications/Naar%20100%20procent%20Open%20Access%20-%20tijdschriftartikelen.pdf>

42. <https://doaj.org/>

Full open access

Another 30% was published in full open access journals that are in the DOAJ. For these journals, there are no consortium agreements. Some of these publishers/journals charge an article processing charge (APC) to the author for making their article openly accessible; others do not (see Community-driven open access).

Publisher-driven open access is generally very convenient for researchers who are affiliated with Dutch institutions: through the big deals, APCs are 'prepaid'; and there are several possibilities for (partial) funding of APCs outside of the deals.

However, there are a number of issues with this route to open access:

- **The APC-model is not equitable.** APC-based open access risks stratifications of publishing as well-resourced researchers can cover even the highest APCs, while less well-resourced researchers cannot. Although many publishers offer fee-waivers and discounts to authors from some countries⁴³, restrictive terms and administrative burden, as well as the extent to which they seemingly place authors in the position of asking for 'charity', mean that they are often criticised as a weak response to an urgent issue⁴⁴.
- **Lack of (digital) autonomy.** A small number of publishers wield enormous market power. This leads to a high risk of vendor lock-in and a weaker position for the UNL/NFU in negotiations with these publishers. The risks of becoming increasingly dependent on a few revenue-driven publishers and their terms of use in all stages of the research life cycle ask for open (not-for-profit) alternatives for digital services and regulation.
- **Lack of transparency in the cost breakdown.** There is great variation in the transparency of 'transformative agreements' where it concerns 1) disclosure of contracts 2) disclosure of total amount involved in the contracts 3) transparency on the division of the total amount between the 'read' and 'publish' part, and/or clarity on how that division is determined. While the information available in publicly available contracts provides a rich source of analysis of the nature and type of contracts, there are too many gaps in the available information to build a comprehensive total picture of publishing costs under transformative agreements⁴⁵.

43. <https://www.research4life.org/access/eligibility/>

44. Ross-Hellauer T. et al. (2022). Dynamics of cumulative advantage and threats to equity in open science: a scoping review. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>

45. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Kramer, B. (2024). Study on scientific publishing in Europe – Development, diversity, and transparency of costs, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/89349>

- **Rising costs for reading and publishing.** A combination of a rising number of publications and market power has led to rising costs for reading and/or publishing, limiting access to reading/publishing for many researchers and hindering public access to research results: APC expenses have sharply increased among six countries with different OA policies (USA, China, UK, France, the Netherlands, and Norway)⁴⁶. Reputation seems to be a commodity that drives researchers to select a certain journal, and publishers set their APC fees accordingly⁴⁷.
- **Opacity of agreements for researchers.** For researchers, the publication landscape with all its different models is opaque. Researchers are usually not aware of the costs of their publication behaviour. If this awareness does exist, it can lead to financial motives prevailing over substantive ones: those affiliated with an institution with an attractive arrangement become co-authors. The choice may fall on the journal for which publishing costs have already been covered.
- **Lack of integral control instruments at the university level.** For a university as a whole, it has become extremely complex to control open access costs integrally: the P&R deals are financed from the collection budgets at the libraries; APCs outside P&R deals are paid from research funds or faculty budgets. There is no place in the university where a complete overview of the sum of these costs is available. Because of the different streams of money, it is also difficult to control costs and transition to other business models integrally. This means that while UNL's ambition is to tightly control cost-neutral P&R deals, the costs for APCs via full gold increase substantially every year.
This leads to a dilemma for the negotiation teams of UNL/UKB: by bringing full gold publishing within the P&R deal with a major publisher, the costs may become transparent, the price cap could become lower, and the institutions spend less overall. However, it also means that more money is tied up in a system that is increasingly being questioned⁴⁸.

46. Zhang, L., Wei, Y., Huang, Y., & Sivertsen, G. (2022). *Scientometrics*, 127, 7653–7679. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04407-5>

47. Budzinski, O., Grebel, T., Wolling, J., & Zhang, X. (2020). Drivers of article processing charges in open access. *Scientometrics*, 124(3), 2185–2206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03578-3>

48. White paper open access, versie 2.0. (2023). UKB Werkgroep Licenties: Matthijs van Otegem en Kurt De Belder

Community-driven open access

Many full open access journals and/or platforms do not charge APCs to authors. Costs for these journals/platforms are usually borne by the academic community, such as societies, universities, libraries, funders or other stakeholders. There are many such journals that serve a rich diversity of academic communities, languages, and publication types ⁴⁹.

To provide journals within the Netherlands with an affordable alternative to APC-based open access, openjournals.nl has been developed: a national open service infrastructure for “editorial entities” (scientific societies, editorial boards, publishers) that offers a fully open-source publication and manuscript workflow system ⁵⁰.

Furthermore, there is a growing number of ‘Netherlands University Presses’ (NUPs, in Leiden, Groningen, Delft, Tilburg, Nijmegen, Maastricht), that focus on community-driven open access as a service for their academic staff. In these NUPS, the publishing operation is seen as an expense in the ongoing budget and is often financed from funds associated with supporting open access and/or open science. The revenues are partly financial (e.g., the sale of printed books), but mainly lie in the broader dissemination and thus societal impact of the scientific results. The international DIAMAS project is mapping the European landscape of these Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) ⁵¹.

Another alternative model is the publish-review-curate (PRC) model, a way of publishing research that makes the most of advances in technology since the print journal: the immediacy and flexibility of today’s communication. It is a transparent and decentralised way of sharing research. In the PRC model, each step can happen independently, in different venues, and more than once.

Publish: Research is made publicly available—usually as a preprint—with minimal gatekeeping, enabling rapid dissemination and early feedback.

Review: Work is openly reviewed by experts, peers from adjacent disciplines, or anyone with relevant insight. Reviews are visible, accountable, and contribute directly to scholarly dialogue.

Curate: Curation can take many forms, from editorial assessments to inclusion in thematic collections. Research communities, editorial groups, and other organisations can validate, contextualise, and highlight work to improve discoverability and trust.

Some organisations are bringing elements of PRC together to create an end-to-end workflow (e.g. eLife, BioPhysics Colab, MetaROR, Gigabyte). The Peer Community In family of journals focuses on recommendations and published evaluations of preprints. Publishing platforms F1000 and Open Research Europe (ORE) also offer PRC.

49. The OA Diamond Journals Study (2021): https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/yejfasey/20210309_coalitions_diamond_study_final.pdf

50. <https://openjournals.nl/>

51. <https://diamasproject.eu/>

The community-driven route to open access is more equitable than APC-based open access (everyone can publish and publishing is disconnected from budgets of faculties/researchers to pay per article), contributes to a pluralistic publication landscape, and is often more compatible with community-governance and retention of ownership of and digital sovereignty over the scholarly work ⁵².

However, this route also has a number of issues:

- **Lack of uptake by the academic community.** Community-driven open access currently only is a relatively small route in the Netherlands. Increasing uptake requires a big shift in publication culture, as prestige and perception of quality now often are connected to 'traditional' publisher journals. Community-driven open access should be recognised and rewarded.
- **Lack of integral and collective approach.** A national line on diamond open access has only just started, with limited (project) funding. An integral, collaborative approach for developing and supporting non-APC-based open access models by Dutch stakeholders is more effective and cost-efficient (avoids duplication and is focused on long-term and sustainable models) ⁵³.
- **Scalability and sustainability.** Many community-driven open access publishers/ infrastructures/ platforms are small and publish a limited number of publications per year ⁵⁴. This poses a challenge for scalability and coordination of the myriad of small entities, and raises concerns about the digital durability of their published works.

Institutional repository-based open access

In 2015, the institutional repository-based route to open access received important legal support. During the review of the Dutch Copyright Law, the 'Taverne amendment' was introduced. This amendment - laid down in article 25fa of the Dutch Copyright Law ⁵⁵ - allows all researchers to share their (short) academic works through a repository after a non-specified embargo-period ⁵⁶. To support researchers who want to make use of this right, the university libraries jointly developed the project "You share, we take care" ⁵⁷.

52. https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/yeifasey/20210309_coalitions_diamond_study_final.pdf

53. UNL, Jansen, D., Sondervan, J. (2023). Versterking ondersteuning van diamond open access in Nederland. https://www.universiteitenvanonderland.nl/files/publications/Notitie%20Versterking%20ondersteuning%20van%20diamond%20open%20access%20in%20Nederland_verseJuli2023.pdf

54. The OA Diamond Journals Study (2021): https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/yeifasey/20210309_coalitions_diamond_study_final.pdf

55. Dutch Copyright Law, article 25fa (2015): <https://wetten.overheid.nl/jci1.3.c:BWBR0001886&hoofdstuk=la&artikel=25fa&z=2021-01-01&g=2021-01-01>

56. Dirk J.G. Visser, "De Open Access bepaling in het auteurscontractenrecht", AML: tijdschrift voor auteurs-, media- en informatierecht 2015 (3): 68-74

57. See: <https://www.openaccess.nl/en/policies/open-access-in-dutch-copyright-law-taverne-amendment>. See also: Arjan Schalken, "Trust as key element in implementing green open access based on Dutch Copyright Law: sharing good practices from the You Share We Take Care pilot", LIBER 2020 - Session #3: Securing and Building Trust, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3921751>.

All Dutch universities and medical centres now make use of this route; most of them have an opt-out policy, which allows for a deposit of the published version in the institutional repository after 6 months. The [Netherlands Research Portal](#) provides the locations of all the full texts of short academic publications in Dutch repositories.

Open access through self-archiving in these repositories is often a fallback option for articles that are not (or cannot be) published open access.

Another flavour of institute-driven open access is the Rights Retention Strategy, which was adopted by cOAlition S funders⁵⁸: they have changed their grant conditions such that their grantees will be mandated to apply a CC BY licence to all submitted Author-Accepted Manuscripts (AAMs) based on their funding. Because the grant conditions predate possible later conditions set by the publisher, this allows cOAlition S-funded researchers to share their work through repositories without restrictions. In a variation of this model, authors are requested by their employers or funders to assign a non-exclusive licence to publish. A policy like this was implemented by the Harvard Faculty of Arts and Sciences in 2008 (Harvard Licensing Model⁵⁹). In the Netherlands, Woutersen et al.⁶⁰ have shown that this model could work in the Dutch context, especially if the copyright is retained by the university's employee⁶¹.

In 2022, 20% of the openly accessible article publications were only accessible through repository-based open access⁶².

However, this route has a number of issues:

- **“You share, we take care” is not funder-compliant.** The implementation of the Taverne amendment at Dutch institutions, with a 6-month embargo period, is not compliant with mandates from many European funders.
- **Rights retention requires action from the author.** This route requires action from the author, as they have to provide an Author-Accepted Manuscript (AAM) for zero-embargo deposition, or have to add rights-retention information to their manuscripts. This puts the author in the middle of the tug-of-war for copyright and sovereignty between funders and institutions on the one hand and publishers on the other.

58. <https://www.coalition-s.org/rights-retention-strategy/>

59. https://osc.hul.harvard.edu/assets/files/model-policy-annotated_12_2015.pdf

60. Woutersen-Windhouwer, S., Van Eeten, D., & de Rooy, A. (2019). Het Harvard Open Access-licentiemodel in het Nederlands recht. *Nederlands Juristen Blad*: <https://www.recht.nl/exit.html?id=298157&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.njb.nl%2Fuploads%2F2019%2F10%2F2707-2712-NJB36-ART02.pdf>

61. Bosman, J., De Jonge, H., Kramer, B., & Sondervan, J. (2021). Advancing open access in the Netherlands after 2020: from quantity to quality. *UKSG Insights*: <https://insights.uksg.org/articles/10.1629/uksg.545>

62. Open Access Monitor 2022: https://www.universiteitennederland.nl/files/publications/UNL%2023048%20U%20-%20OCW%20-%20%20Monitor%20Open%20Access%202022%20en%20vervolg_0_0.pdf

